

PREPARATION OF THE PVDF/PAR COMPOSITES WITH HIGH SHEAR RATE PROCESSING AND HYBRIDIZATION

Seung Goo Lee^{1,*}, Hyeon Soo Lim¹, Jong Sung Won¹, and Woo Jin Oh¹

¹ Department of Organic Materials & Textile System Engineering, Chungnam National University, Daejeon, Republic of Korea

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ABSTRACT

Piezoelectric composites were prepared using the blends of piezoelectric PVDF and PAR having excellent mechanical properties. To overcome the immiscibility of PVDF and PAR, PAR dispersed with high shear rate processing and BaTiO₃ was added into the blend to improve the piezoelectricity.

1 INTRODUCTION

Energy harvesting technology is a technology that is widely used in wearable devices and mobile products in the way of acquiring electric energy from energy such as light, heat, vibration existing in nature. Among the energy harvesting methods, piezoelectric elements that obtain electric energy through vibration and pressure are getting the most attention. As a piezoelectric material, a ceramic material having a large dielectric constant is widely used. However, the piezoelectric material of the ceramic system has a disadvantage of brittleness which is difficult to process and weak to impact. Therefore, in order to overcome these disadvantages, researches have been conducted to develop a piezoelectric material using a polymer having piezoelectric characteristics.

PVDF(polyvinylidene fluoride) has been known as a functional polymer having piezoelectric properties, and thus there have been much of studies to elucidate the characteristics and applications of this material.[1-10] However, it has poor mechanical properties for applying structural parts of the skeleton robotics or energy harvesting structures. [10-13] Therefore, a certain kind of reinforcing is essential for enhancing mechanical properties of the PVDF.

In this study, in order to manufacture the high strength piezoelectric composites, liquid crystalline polymer PAR (polyarylate), which has excellent mechanical properties was blended with PVDF. However, since PAR and PVDF are immiscible, the PVDF/PAR composite were manufactured with high shear rate processing to reduce the size of the dispersed phase in the blend. Changes of the PVDF/PAR composite properties were analyzed according to the high shear rate processing conditions and PAR content. Also, to improve the piezoelectricity, BaTiO₃ having high piezoelectricity was added to composites.

2 EXPERIMENTALS

2.1 Materials

The materials used in this study are PVDF (Kynar 720, Arkema), PAR (Vectra A950, Celanese). Tri (2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphite (Sigma Aldrich) was used as an antioxidant during extrusion and Barium titanate (BaTiO₃)(SigmaAldrich) was used as a ceramic powder to improve piezoelectricity.

2.1 Composite fabrication

Preparation of the PVDF/PAR blends was conducted by using a high shear rate extruder (NHSS2-28, Niigata). PAR content in the PVDF was set at 10 to 50 wt% for blending. Experiments were divided two methods. One is a simple high shear extrusion of the mixture of PAR and PVDF. The other one is consisted of 2 steps of the extrusion. In 1st step, PAR only processed in high shear extrusion, and then the extrusion of the PAR/PVDF at normal shear condition was conducted. High shear rate processing was conducted in the range of 1000 to 3000 rpm while normal extrusion is set at 225 rpm of the twin

screw speed. Fig.1 and Table.1 showed the schematic of high shear rate process and the parameter of high shear rate.

Figure 1 Schematic of high shear rate processing

Condition	Variables
PVDF/PAR (wt %)	5/5, 7/3, 8/2, 9/1
Shear rate (RPM)	1000, 2000
Mixing time (sec)	20
Antioxidant (phr)	1
Temperature (°C)	320

Table 1 Parameter of high shear rate processing

2.2 PVDF/PAR/BaTiO₃ composite fabrication

BaTiO₃ was added to PVDF/PAR composites to improve piezoelectricity. First, high shear rate extrusion of PAR was conducted. Composite of PVDF and BaTiO₃ was prepared by dispersing BaTiO₃ powder in a polymer solution in which PVDF is dissolved in DMF. At this time, BaTiO₃ was added in an amount of 1 to 10 wt% of the total solution. DMF is removed from the solution and the PVDF / BaTiO₃ remaining is extruded again with the PAR which was conducted high shear extrusion. The extrusion is set at 225 rpm of the twin screw speed.

Figure 2 Schematic of preparation of PVDF/BaTiO₃ composite

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Thermal properties of the PVDF/PAR composites

PAR / PVDF composites were measured by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) to analyze the change of glass transition temperature. The analysis was carried out at 25 °C to 350 °C with a temperature rise and a cooling rate of 10 °C / min under a nitrogen atmosphere. Glass transition temperature (T_g) of the PVDF/PAR composite processed with high shear extrusion showed no big difference according to the PAR content. But compared to the normal extrusion condition, T_g of the PVDF/PAR composite processed with high shear extrusion showed a decreasing trend because of the increase of the miscibility between PVDF and PAR.

In order to confirm the compatibility of PVDF / PAR, it was analyzed using TGA. The analysis was carried out at a heating rate of 10 °C / min from 25 °C to 800 °C. When PVDF / PAR was normally blended, two steps were performed during pyrolysis. However, it was confirmed that the composite conducted to the high shear rate process showed a pyrolysis behavior close to one step rather than two steps.

Figure 3 Pyrolysis behavior of PVDF/PAR composite with high shear rate processing

3.2 Morphology of the PVDF/PAR composites

In order to confirm the variation of dispersed phase according to various manufacturing conditions of the PVDF/PAR composite material, cross section of composite material was observed at 5,000 times using SEM. The cross section of the composite material was observed after the specimen was broken with sufficiently cooled with liquid nitrogen. In the case of not carrying out the high shear rate process, it was confirmed that the dispersed phase was unstable as the content of PAR increased. However, when the high shear rate process was conducted, it was confirmed that even if the PAR content was increased, the dispersed phase was evenly distributed. Figure.4 shows a cross-section of the PVDF / PAR composite material identified by SEM.

Figure 4 SEM images of PVDF/PAR blends at 20 wt%; (a) normal blend; (b) shear rate 1000 rpm; (c) shear rate 2000 rpm

3.3 Mechanical properties of the PVDF/PAR composites

Tensile test was carried out in accordance with ASTM D 638 to confirm the mechanical properties of PVDF / PAR composites prepared under various conditions. The test was conducted using an Instron 4467 and the cross-head speed was set at 10 mm / min. Fig.5 shows tensile strength of the PVDF/PAR composite materials; AF refers to a sample in which both PVDF and PAR are conducted to a high shear rate process at the same time; A refers to a sample in which only PAR is conducted to a high shear rate process. In Fig.5, the PVDF/PAR composite processed with normal extrusion(225-AF) showed a decreasing trend of the tensile strength according to the PAR content. Contrastingly, the PVDF/PAR composite processed with high shear extrusion showed almost a reverse trend of the tensile strength. This result comes from the improved miscibility between the PAR and PVDF by high shear processing for introducing smaller dispersed phase(PAR) in the PVDF matrix. The addition of BaTiO₃ to enhance piezoelectricity interfered with the compatibility of PVDF and PAR, and so, the average tensile strength decreased with increasing BaTiO₃ content.

In order to analyze the flexural properties of PVDF / PAR composites, INSTRON 4467 was used in accordance with ASTM D 790. Using a 3-point jig, the centre of composite material was subjected to a load at a cross-head speed of 2mm/min. In the case of the normal blend, the compatibility of PVDF and PAR was not good, indicating that the bending properties were reduced by phase separation. However, in case of composite material conducted to high shear rate process, the compatibility is improved and the bending property is increased due to the reinforcing effect. However, the high shear process at 2000 rpm tended to reduce the flexural properties due to the damage of PVDF.

Figure 5 Tensile strength of the PVDF/PAR composites with PAR content

3.4 Piezoelectric properties of the PVDF/PAR composites

The PVDF show excellent piezoelectricity when the ratio of β -crystals is highest among the crystal structure of α , β , γ and δ . The piezoelectric properties of PVDF / PAR composites were measured using a multimeter. At this time, the PVDF/PAR ratio was fixed to 8:2 and the comparison was carried out.

When only PAR was undergone high shear rate process, PVDF/PAR composite showed constant piezoelectric characteristics at 2 ~ 3 V. It has been confirmed that it has a constant value since it does not affect the PVDF beta crystal. However, in the case of a composite material in which both PAR and PVDF are conducted to high shear rate processing, the high heat and shear rate appears to reduce the piezoelectricity of the composite because it relaxes the beta crystal of PVDF.

In order to improve the piezoelectric properties, it was confirmed that the piezoelectric properties were increased up to 3 times according to the BaTiO₃ content when the ceramic powder, BaTiO₃, was added to the composite material.

4 CONCLUSIONS

From the results of this study, we can conclude followings: As processing with high-shear rate method, tensile and flexural properties of the PVDF were improved largely. Also, the size of dispersed phase of PAR in PVDF matrix decreased. However, mechanical properties and the β -phase crystal content of PVDF decreased due to the degradation at high screw speed condition over than 2000 rpm. Therefore, it can be confirmed that the high shear processing caused the improvement of compatibility until appropriate condition, and however excessive high shear condition, degradation of the blends were caused. In the case of piezoelectric characteristics, it was confirmed that piezoelectricity decreased because it affects β crystalline of PVDF under high shear conditions. In addition, piezoelectric properties greatly increased when inorganic materials were added to improve piezoelectricity, while the mechanical properties of the composites were reduced by the inclusion of BaTiO₃ powder.

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